

CRITICAL SUCCESS FACTORS IN IMPLEMENTATION OF SIX SIGMA PROJECT AT IDEA CELLULAR LIMITED

*Alok Kumar Mittal

* *Research Scholar, AIMA-AMU, Joint PhD program, New Delhi, India*

Abstract

This research aims to identify critical success factors in six sigma implementation in a service-oriented organization Idea Cellular Limited in India. The company has recently implemented a six sigma project. A semi-structured interview was conducted to identify the critical success factors responsible for the successful implementation of the project.

The paper is organized in the following manner: the first section provides the background of selected literature in the field of six sigma in service sector and critical success factors available in the literature. Next, the research objectives and methodology are described, followed by the results, discussion and finally the study limitations and indication for further research.

Keywords: *Six sigma, GPRS, CSAT, COPIS,*

*Corresponding author: * Alok Kumar Mittal

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INTRODUCTION

Over the last two decades, the industrial organizations throughout the world have adopted a large variety of management programmes enhancing their competitiveness. Six sigma is one of the most popular programmes and is based on many statistical tools and techniques. The goal of six sigma is value creation through reducing defects in quality and elimination of variation. The elimination of variation in the process removes the defect. "A defect is defined as anything which could lead to customer dissatisfaction" (Antony, 2004). Six sigma improves the efficiency and effectiveness of business processes by reducing waste and costs resulting from poor quality.

Motorola created six sigma in mid 80s to improve the performance of key processes, productivity and quality and at the same time to reduce costs (Bhote and Bhote, 1991). The concept of six sigma was subsequently adopted by many big organizations across the globe including GE, Allied Signal, Honeywell, Bombardier, ABB, Sony in manufacturing sector and J P Morgan, American Express, Lloyds TSB, Egg, City Bank, BT, etc. (Antony, 2006; Coronado and Antony, 2002). The key driver behind the development of six sigma was the need for quality improvement during manufacturing complex products involving a large number of parts with a high probability of defects in the end product (Dale et al., 2007). The external driver in the form of demands from customers to improve the quality in final product supported for continuous improvement.

There is a myth that six sigma is only limited to manufacturing organizations and has a limited spread in service industries. A reason behind limited spread of six sigma in service industries is that many service processes are "unseen, intangible and even unmeasurable" (Chakrabarty and Tan, 2007). This thinking has been proved to be wrong at least for health care, banking and call center where six sigma has been successfully implemented to improve processes and reduce waste (Hensley and Dobie, 2005).

This research aims to identify critical success factors in six sigma implementation in a service-oriented organization Idea Cellular Limited in India. The company has recently implemented a

six sigma project. A semi-structured interview was conducted with Mr. Mohammad Iqbal, Vertical Head, (Quality) to identify the critical success factors responsible for the successful implementation of the project.

The paper is organized in the following manner: the first section provides the background of selected literature in the field of six sigma in service sector and critical success factors available in the literature. Next, the research objectives and methodology are described, followed by the results, discussion and finally the study limitations and indication for further research.

BACKGROUND

Although six sigma has drawn much attention and recognition in manufacturing organizations still the service-oriented organizations stay away from six sigma considering it as a manufacturing solution (Antony et al 2007). In manufacturing organizations, six sigma is implemented through measurable and quantifiable processes and established quality management programmes. In contrast to this, in service industries, the processes are not very well understood and controlled.

Many organizations have reported significant benefits as a result of six sigma implementation. General Electric and Motorola claim to have benefits more than \$ 2 billion after successful implementation of six sigma projects (Coronado and Antony, 2002). However there may be examples where the success has not been so great. Additionally, many organizations reporting success of the six sigma project come under the category of manufacturing organizations. These contrast results indicate that there are some critical success factors which make the implementation of a six sigma project a success or a failure in an organization. Critical success factors are those factors which are very important to the success of any project and if the objectives of these factors are not met, the project is a failure (Rockart, 1979).

Management involvement and commitment is the most important factor in six sigma implementation (Henderson and Evans, 2000). In success stories of Motorola, General Electric and Allied signal, it was the CEO who played a critical role in success (Harry and Schroeder, 2000). Halliday (2001) also asserts of the top management commitment. Cultural change is the other important factor in success of six sigma implementation. The people involved with the process make many excuses and create resistance to change. A good communication plan shared with the employees reduces the resistance to change (Henderson and Evans, 2000) and hence communication is another important factor in the success of six sigma project. In order to successfully implement the six sigma project, some organizational characteristics such as communication skills, long term focus and strategy and teamwork need to be in place. In addition to this, the organization should have enough resources and investment (Coronado and Antony, 2002).

Training is other crucial factor in six sigma. It provides "an opportunity to people to improve their comfort level through training classes" (Hendricks and Kelbaugh, 1998). Linking six sigma to business strategy is another necessary factor related with successful implementation. It needs to be clear how projects and other activities link to customers, core processes and competitiveness (Pande et al., 2000). Customer "needs" is the main focus of six sigma. "Six sigma projects should begin and end with the customer" (Coronado and Antony, 2002). Other critical success factors cited in literature include tools and techniques of six sigma, human resource, suppliers, project management skills, project prioritization and selection.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The primary objective of the research was to identify critical success factors in six sigma project implementation in an Indian company named Idea Cellular Limited. The research question is defined below:

“What are the critical success factors in implementation of six sigma project in Idea Cellular Limited?”

Other specific questions were outlined, in order to define the research area:

- What were the steps in six sigma implementation in Idea Cellular Limited?
- What was the success criteria used by the company for evaluating the six sigma project implementation?
- What were the benefits of implementation of six sigma project in the company?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The company: Idea Cellular Limited

Idea Cellular Limited is a company of Aditya Birla Group – India’s first truly multinational corporation. It controls a portfolio of India's most attractive and contiguous telecom geographies. Idea provides the telecom services such as landline, mobile services, internet services and GPRS applications for the individual and business customers in India. The company has a pan India presence in offering the telecom services. Idea Cellular accesses over 60% of India's total telephony potential and is operating in thirteen states. Idea has employee strength of more than 300 in its Jaipur circle where the project was implemented. (www.ideacellular.com)

Semi-structured interview

In order to perform the research, a semi-structured interview was conducted in Idea, with Mr. Mohammad Iqbal, Vertical Head (Quality), a Black Belt and directly involved with six sigma project implementation in Idea Cellular Limited. It was also written to the company to give the permission for one other employee’s interview but did not get the favorable response from the company.

“An interview is a purposeful discussion between two or more people” (Kahn and Cannell, 1957 as cited in Saunders et al., 2003). “The interview is probably the most widely employed method in qualitative research” (Bryman and Bell, 2003). The flexibility of an interview makes it an attractive option than any other data collection method. The interviews may be classified in

different categories such as structured, semi-structured and unstructured or in-depth interviews based on their administering techniques.

Semi-structured interviews are non-standardized interviews, while structured interviews are standardized interviews. Since the purpose of structured interviews is to collect quantifiable data so they are also known as quantitative research interviews. In contrast, semi-structured interviews are known as qualitative research interviews (Saunders et al., 2003).

In semi-structured interview, the researcher has a list of themes and questions. The researcher has the flexibility to alter these themes and questions during the interview. He even can omit or add few of the questions if required depending on the organizational context and sequence of questions may also vary “depending on the flow of conversation” (Saunders et al., 2003). The interviewee also has flexibility in replying to the questions (Bryman and Bell, 2003). In comparison to semi-structured interviews, the questions asked in structured interviews are in form of a predetermined set and the sequence can not be changed during the interview.

Semi-structured interviews are used in qualitative research to address ‘what’, ‘how’ and ‘why’. The more emphasis is put on exploring ‘why’ (Saunders et al., 2003). This interview method was very relevant in the present research context, in which the research area was ‘what are the critical success factors and how and why they were important in six sigma implementation’. The semi-structured interview explored and provided the information about the process of six sigma project implementation in the company. The available theoretical background in the literature helped in preparing the “interview guide” for the semi-structured interview.

The interview was structured by synthesis of the literature and the following questions were asked:

- a) Why did the company decide to implement this particular six sigma project?
- b) Could you describe the steps followed in the six sigma implementation process?
- c) What were the criteria adopted to measure success?
- d) Do you think whether the project was a success?

- e) In your opinion, what was critical to ensure successful implementation of six sigma project in the company?

The interview was conducted on phone lasting approximately an hour and recorded for later analysis. The interview was transcribed for better understanding and analysis.

The analysis involved repeated listening to the recorded interview and synthesis of the transcript, followed by the identification of connections between different strands of data and comparison with the success factors already mentioned in the literature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Process of six sigma implementation in Idea

Idea has been implementing the total quality management for quite a long time to improve the quality of their services and to address the needs of the customers. Since Six sigma is the latest tool in the arsenal focusing on the customer “needs”, hence the management decided to implement the six sigma project in the company. Proper training as a necessary step of the six sigma project was provided at all levels of the employees. According to Mr. Iqbal, before six sigma implementation, the company faced the problems on many fronts. One of the major pain areas of the company was the incomplete application forms. Mr. Iqbal described the various steps involved in the six sigma project implementation.

As per regulatory norms for a new prepaid connection complete application form alongwith customer identity proof documents is a mandatory requirement. The company had to bar the outgoing calls of the customer whose application forms were incomplete or were without the identity proof or address proof. This was a high pain area for the company and impacts the CSAT level, company’s revenue and the health of the process.

According to Mr. Iqbal, a project charter for this project was prepared, in which the necessary information was recorded. It included the names of the team members including sponsor, champion, project leader and a black belt. In the ‘Define’ step the toll gate dates were agreed upon for implementation of different steps. Specific problem statement was defined and scope of

work was also decided to finalize the in scope and out of scope work. The financial impact as the result of the project was also estimated and recorded. High level process maps such as COPIS were drawn.

In the ‘Measure’ and ‘Analyse’ steps, the regionwise compliance was measured. The current sigma level and yield of the process was ascertained. A drill was carried out to find out the reasons for non-compliance. The analysis was carried out till the distributors and retailers end to diagnose the actual reasons responsible for non-compliance. Similarly, those distributors and retailers were targeted whose compliance level was very low as compared to others. In addition to this the field audit was done to find out the root causes of delay in the field. The time study was carried out for retailers in different class cities to find out the actual time taken for delivery of the documents.

In the ‘Improve’ step, the actions were taken based on the analysis done in the previous steps. The various improvement actions included the picking up of the documents from the ‘A’ class retailers. The ‘B’ class retailers were instructed to deliver the documents by courier to reach on time. The other improvement actions included proper training given to the distributors and retailers.

In the ‘Control’ step all the actions were documented and it was ensured that the employees do not deviate from the best practices.

Critical Success Factors in implementation of six sigma project at Idea

When asked about the success criteria adopted by the company, the quality manager mentioned that the main criterion was increase in regulatory compliance from current level of 60% to 80%. The number of customers whose outgoing calls were barred because of non-compliance came down significantly. This all led to the retention of the customers because of increase in their satisfaction level. This all led to increase in the profitability of the company. In addition to this, Mr. Iqbal mentioned that increase in the satisfaction level of all the customers in the process was another success measure.

When asked about the factors that were crucial for the success of the implementation of the project, Mr. Iqbal cited the first most important factor as the commitment of CEO to the project

and in implementation of the improvement actions. He said since the six sigma project involves the cross functional teams in execution of the project, hence the involvement of CEO becomes very crucial to improve the cohesiveness of the team and in successful implementation of the project.

The second most important factor was organizational culture and the change management. Mr. Iqbal says, "It is easy to change everything except humans". The people involved in the process are very hard to change their old practices. They create stiff resistance by saying "we have tried it before" or "we are in the system for last so many years". The organizational culture plays a major role in change management because in many organizations the culture is fearful however in others it provides an opportunity to change. In six sigma, defects are seen as improvement opportunities (Erwin, 2000). According to Mr. Iqbal, "The personal relations of the six sigma team with the process people also play a very critical role in successful implementation of the project". The persuasion and motivation to change the process and people come from human interaction and personal relations.

Training of the employees at all levels is another critical factor in the successful implementation of the six sigma project. The training starts with the top management such as sponsors and walks down through the organizational hierarchy. The training provides an opportunity to communicate all the know-how of six sigma to all the employees and improve their comfort level (Hendricks and Kelbaugh 1998).

During the training the employees learn team tools, process tools and leadership tools. Mr. Iqbal says, "A strong team leader is a must for successful implementation of any six sigma project". The leader directs the team in the right direction and coordinates among various head of departments for successful implementation. In the absence of an effective leader probably the project may fail. Mr. Iqbal asserts that meetings are also necessary, since at least half of the process problems are solved during initial meetings of the project. Project management skills are another ingredient in effective implementation of six sigma project. Most of the projects fail due to poor management skills and determining the meeting's roles and responsibilities (Eckes, 2000).

When asked about link with business strategy, Mr. Iqbal says, “Six sigma is not a standalone activity”. It is a whole philosophy and not merely use of tools and techniques for quality improvement (Dale, 2007). Every project should be linked with the business strategy. The cost benefit analysis for all the projects should be carried out and it should demonstrate its alignment with the business strategy.

Six sigma projects begin and end with the customer. Customers are the major focus of the projects. First of all, the customer “needs” or critical-to-quality characteristics are identified in the starting phase of the project and this is how the six sigma projects are linked with the customers.

Company resources and infrastructure play a very essential role in the successful implementation of the project. According to Mr. Iqbal, “The success of any six sigma project depends on the resources provided for a particular project”. Motivation in the form of good career growth and incentives are necessary for effective manpower.

The success of any project also depends on its identification, prioritization and selection. Since there is always an array of projects required for process improvement and customer satisfaction, it becomes very critical to prioritize and finally select a suitable project. According to Mr. Iqbal, “We selected this compliance of regulatory requirement project out of available projects because this project helped us in improving the customer satisfaction and profitability of company”.

CONCLUSION

“Six sigma today has evolved from merely a measurement of quality to an overall business improvement strategy for a large number of companies around the world” (Antony, 2006 (1)). It is not only being used in manufacturing organizations but is also being embraced by the large service oriented companies. This paper tried to identify the critical success factors for the successful implementation of six sigma project in a telecom company in India. It was found out with the help of synthesis of literature and from the discussion with the quality manager of the company that these factors are very important and need to be taken into account for getting the effective financial results from the six sigma project.

However, these factors are the result of viewpoint of only one manager in a telecom company, hence it is difficult to generalize them to other companies or industries without further research. Further research can be conducted in other companies from the same industry in different environments and cultures in order to compare the results obtained from this research. The other staff of the company could not be contacted without the approval of the management.

In addition to this, these factors are related with the service industry and hence there is further scope to identify the critical success factors for manufacturing industries.

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